

Toxigenic microalgae and co-occurrence of toxins in Patagonian Gulfs of Argentina

Leilén Luciana Gracia Villalobos^{1*}, Norma Herminia Santinelli², Alicia Viviana Sastre², Noelia Mariel Uyua², Soledad Díaz Ovejero², Emiliano Agustín Crippa², Bernd Krock³

¹Laboratorio de Química Ambiental y Ecotoxicología (LAQUIAE), Centro para el Estudio de Sistemas Marinos (CESIMAR) – CONICET, Boulevard Brown 2915, (9120) Puerto Madryn, Chubut, Argentina; ²Instituto de Investigación de Hidrobiología, FCNyCS, UNPSJB, Gales 48, (9100) Trelew, Chubut, Argentina; ³Alfred Wegener Institut-Helmholtz Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung, Chemische Ökologie, Am Handelshafen 12, 27570 Bremerhaven, Germany.

*corresponding author's email: gracia@cenpat-conicet.gob.ar

Abstract

In the coastal waters of Chubut Province in Argentina, several species of toxigenic microalgae have been recorded. Among those, the dinoflagellate *Alexandrium catenella* has caused poisonings and human deaths since 1980, resulting in closures of mollusk fisheries due to the presence of paralytic shellfish toxins (PST). In recent years, in addition to PST outbreaks, fishery closures have also been imposed due to lipophilic toxins above regulatory limits in shellfish. Phytoplankton analyses were performed during 2018 at six sites located in the North Patagonian gulfs (San Matías, San José, and Nuevo). Between February and June, the presence of toxins and toxic species was assessed. Domoic acid (DA) was detected in 47% of the samples, while the pectentoxins (PTX) PTX-2 and/or PTX-2sa were detected in 79% of the samples. The co-occurrence of both toxins was observed during all months except March. The diatoms *Pseudo-nitzschia pungens*, *P. fraudulenta*, and *P. calliantha* were identified as the potential DA producers, while the dinoflagellates *Dinophysis tripos* and *D. acuminata* were identified as the potential producers of PTX. This study expands the knowledge on the simultaneous presence of multiple phycotoxins in the North Patagonian gulfs and raises questions about the possible impacts of such occurrences on public health. This study was carried out in the frame of the Provincial Plan for Prevention and Control of Red Tides.

Keywords: Southwest Atlantic, bioaccumulation, phycotoxins, harmful algal blooms, monitoring
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Introduction

Several toxigenic microalgae species have been recorded along the coast of the Chubut Province (Argentina) since 1980 (Carreto *et al.*, 1981), and they have caused many harmful algal bloom (HAB) events. The most frequent toxin-producing species are: *Alexandrium catenella*, paralytic shellfish toxin (PST)-producing species; *Dinophysis tripos*, *D. acuminata*, *D. caudata*, *D. fortii*, *D. acuta*, *Phalacroma rotundata*, and *Prorocentrum lima*, lipophilic shellfish toxin (LST)-producing species; and *Pseudo-nitzschia australis*, *P. multiseriis*, *P. pungens*, *P. fraudulenta*, and *P. calliantha*, amnesic shellfish toxin (AST)-producing species (Sastre *et al.*, 2018). The species *A. catenella* and members of the genus *Dinophysis* cause toxin-related harmful events, including direct impact on human health or natural resources

or indirect impact to the aquaculture industry. It should be considered that recent studies in different areas of the Argentine Sea have indicated the presence of new groups of phycotoxins in samples of phytoplankton and mollusks. These phycotoxins are produced by various genera of dinoflagellates, such as yessotoxins, spirolides, and azaspiracids (Almandoz *et al.*, 2014, 2019; Akselman *et al.*, 2015; Krock *et al.*, 2015; Turner and Goya, 2015; Tillmann *et al.*, 2016; Fabro *et al.*, 2017, 2019; Guinder *et al.*, 2018; Montoya *et al.*, 2021). Likewise, the list of toxigenic species in the Argentine Sea continues to increase, as is the case with the recent detection of *Prorocentrum texanum* off the coast of the Province of Buenos Aires (Sunesen *et al.*, 2020).

Fig. 1. Distribution of harmful microalgae and shellfish harvest closure due to LST in the North Patagonian gulfs San Matias (SMG), San José (SJG) and Nuevo (NG). Sampling stations: 1 = Puerto Lobos, 2 = Bengoa, 3 = Larralde, 4 = Riacho, 5 = Pardelas, 6 = Playa Paran

The primary aim of this study was to analyze the spatiotemporal distribution of toxigenic microalgae and co-occurrence of toxins present in the Northern Patagonian gulfs.

Material and Methods

Phytoplankton sampling was carried out during 2018 in the North Patagonian gulfs (between 41° and 43° S) San Matías, San José and Nuevo. These are located on the North-eastern coast of the Chubut Province, in Argentina. Samples were collected monthly at the stations Puerto Lobos (San Matías Gulf), Bengoa, Larralde and Riacho (San José Gulf), and Playa Paraná, and Pardelas (Nuevo Gulf), in the frame of the monitoring program.

Water samples for quantitative phytoplankton analyses were collected using a sampling tube with 80 cm of length and 11 cm of diameter. The 250 mL samples were preserved with Lugol's acid solution and stored in the dark. Qualitative phytoplankton samples were taken using a 25 µm mesh net through oblique tows and fixed with formaldehyde at a final concentration of 4%.

A sampling survey to collect phytoplankton for toxin analysis was carried out between February and June in the study area. Phytoplankton samples were collected by oblique net tows from 5 m depth to the surface with a 25 µm mesh net. Ten-milliliter aliquots of the captured material were preserved in Lugol's solution for microscopic observation and used to calculate cell concentrations. The rest of each sample was filtered through Whatman GF/F filters and frozen (-20 °C) until further analysis. Phytoplanktonic species were morphologically identified and counted in a phase-contrast inverted microscope

(Leica DMIL, Wetzlar, Germany). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations of the samples were done with a JSM-6360 LV (Jeol, Tokyo, Japan) at the Facultad de Ciencias Naturales y Museo, Universidad Nacional de La Plata, to identify *Pseudo-nitzschia* species.

Toxin analyses were performed by liquid chromatography coupled to a tandem mass spectrometer (LC-MS/MS), as described in Krock *et al.* (2008).

Results and Discussion

Distribution spatial-temporal of harmful microalgae: relative abundance and cell density

During the summer (January), resting cysts of *A. catenella* were observed in the San José Gulf, and in late winter (August) and spring (October and November), the motile form in Nuevo and San José gulfs. However, no PSTs were recorded in mollusk samples.

Dinophysis tripos was observed from January and presented a maximum concentration of 6,720 cells L⁻¹ in March. In autumn (May-June), lipophilic toxins were recorded in mollusk samples through mouse bioassays in the San Matías and San José (Bengoa and Larralde) gulfs. *Dinophysis acuminata*, *D. fortii*, and *D. caudata* were observed only in net samples with low relative abundances.

During spring and summer, *P. pungens*, *P. fraudulenta*, and *P. calliantha* were present in gulf San José and Nuevo. *P. calliantha* was the most abundant, with maximum values of around 10⁵ cells L⁻¹, contributing to more than 80% of the total phytoplankton (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Cell abundances of toxigenic microalgae in phytoplankton samples and amount of lipophilic and amnesic toxins.

Toxin analyses and species distribution

Qualitative plankton samples from different locations were taken, and *Dinophysis* and *Pseudo-nitzschia* cells were enumerated, and lipophilic and amnesic toxins were determined. Of the LST-producing species, only *D. tripos* and *Phalacrocoma rotundata* were detected, although the latter was recorded in very low density and only in one sample. Of the amnesic shellfish toxin-producing species, *P. fraudulenta*, *P. calliantha*, and *P. pungens* were detected.

The lipophilic toxin profiles in all samples consisted mainly of pectenotoxins PTX-2 followed by PTX-2sa, which were detected in 79% of them. Domoic acid (DA) was detected in 47% of the samples (Fig. 2).

Toxigenic phytoplankton species were recorded throughout 2018 in the North Patagonian gulfs. Although these species have been previously reported for this region (Santinelli *et al.*, 2002; Gracia Villalobos *et al.*, 2015; Sastre *et al.*, 2018), the co-occurrence of toxigenic species of different genera during the greater part of the year has not been reported before. The presence of lipophilic toxin profiles in plankton samples is in accordance with previous reports by Gracia Villalobos *et al.* (2015). In addition, the detection of DA was previously recorded in plankton samples from Nuevo Gulf by Sastre *et al.* (2007). However, this is the first time that simultaneous presence of lipophilic toxins and DA has been reported in plankton samples.

These results highlight the need to permanently update the monitoring programs to mitigate the adverse effects of HAB events on human health, shellfish fisheries, aquaculture, and tourism. In addition, they contribute to know the importance of the transfer and accumulation of phycotoxins to higher levels in the food web in the North Patagonian gulfs.

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